

Different approaches to determining the employer brand were analyzed. The main components of the employer brand were identified. It is customary to divide the components of the employer brand into tangible and intangible ones. Material ones include wages, official employment, the material system of motivation. Intangible components are additional benefits, office, rating, and reputation of a company, type of activity of a company, the possibility of training and development. A tendency of the lack of information to form the employer brand for Generation Z was detected. Generation Z is the people born in 1997–2012. The list of value propositions of employers in the labor market for Generation Z was analyzed. The results of our own research – a survey among students (1341 respondents) having or not having experience – were analyzed. To analyze the results of the survey, mathematical expectation, root mean square deviation, and coefficient of variation of expert evaluation results were used. The rating of the components of the employer brand and their integrated scores in terms of attractiveness for Generation Z were established. The aspects to which employers need primarily to pay attention to for forming a value proposition in the labor market when selecting personnel were established

This study is important because the main components of the employer brand and their priority for Generation Z were not investigated in the scientific field.

As a result of the study, companies were rated by their attractiveness as a place of work or internship in retail and FMCG (fast-moving consumer goods) spheres.

These data can be used by HR-brand agencies, HR departments of international and national companies. Using the results of the survey of the formation of the employer brand for Generation Z will allow enterprises to take into account the expectations of their target audience

Keywords: employment of students, labor market, labor distribution, internal brand, organization of HR management, employer brand

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ANALYSIS OF EMPLOYER BRAND FOR YOUNG PEOPLE

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1. Introduction

The formation of the employer brand is an urgent issue for company positioning in the labor market, creating its reputation, and maintaining its image. This is due to the importance for each company to provide itself with the staff of the necessary intellectual and emotional level that is ready to develop along with the company development. The COVID-19 pandemic has affected the employer market and created new approaches to the work of employees. Companies are gradually recovering from the crisis due to a change in the business model, job cuts, and the creation of new products and services. In addition, human resource managers face a new challenge – to motivate and organize remote work of employees. In 2020, 8.8 % of employees worldwide lost their jobs. As a result, the employees in the region of Europe and Central Asia suffered from redundancy most of all. The International Labor Organization predicts that unemployment will be reduced to 75 million in 2021 and to 23 million in 2022. In the scientific sphere, new tasks appear: to investigate the influence of external circumstances on the formation of the employer brand during remote work of employees, to identify new components of the brand, to analyze channels of communication with the target audience of the brand.

As a result, the formation of the employer brand is very important and requires well-grounded management decisions. First of all, remote work influenced its components and the format of reporting to employees and potential candidates. Secondly, employees choose a company to work for, looking at intangible components of motivation during remote work. That is why companies have the challenge to differ from other companies in the

labor market, help the employees who work from home to feel the values, mission, and spirit of the company. The value proposition of the employer brand should also include components for the employee's family. The factor of communication with employees during a crisis is becoming important. The "small talk" format in the chat with colleagues or during a video call is a result of the transformation of the "small talk" format over coffee in the office. A new trend in companies is the preservation of the mental and physical health of employees. Of course, most companies are primarily concerned about physical health.

However, employees have a new challenge – to improve the skills of time management, because the usual 9 to 18 framework of the working day is disappearing.

Formation of the employer brand for students, in our case it is mostly Generation Z, needs more research. It is necessary to take into account the specific characteristics of the behavior of Generation Z in the process of creating a working environment during remote work and choosing components of the employer brand for young people.

Generation Z has more advanced digital skills and starts working earlier compared to Generation Y. However, remote work helps students to combine work and study. According to the research by Dell Technologies in 2020, 20 % of employees are representatives of Generation Z. That is why there is a need to identify the main components of the value proposition of an employer for students when they are looking for a would-be job.

That is why scientific research into the formation of an employer brand for Generation Z under the influence of COVID-19 is relevant.

2. Literature review and problem statement

Paper [1] states the need to attract candidates with the necessary set of skills and knowledge and create all conditions for each employee to feel the brand and mission of the company, as well as to ensure the implementation of the set goals. But for modern companies that hire representatives of Generation Z, knowledge, skills and understanding of the goals and mission of the company is an important, but not a decisive factor. For them, creativity, information literacy, emotional intelligence are the most desirable parameters for potential job candidates.

Research [2] showed that branding includes two areas: marketing and management of the staff who is involved in work. This indicates two dimensions of the formation of the employer brand: regarding its creation and management in the activities of an enterprise. The employer brand and the company's brand, despite having many features in common, still differ significantly. To form the employer brand for Generation Z, the priority is not marketing, but rather part of personnel management that is responsible for its development and determines the possibility of building a career.

The authors of [3] believe that the employer brand should be considered more broadly since the strategy of forming the employer brand is the first strategy. The strategy helps to manage human resources, ensures the competitiveness of an enterprise in the market, and allows remaining successful leaders. However, there is a need to determine the causes and prerequisites for the influence of the employer brand on the financial results of a company.

According to [4], the employer brand includes the process where a company and its employees sign an agreement according to which a potential employee has a reason to become part of the company's team and a company has a reason to hire an applicant. This approach is very simplified, it is the identification of these reasons that is necessary to form effective value propositions.

The main characteristics of the employer brand are given in [4], in particular: economic, including compensation and benefits, functional (when an employee receives a certain skill), psychological (self-identification, comparison with the status of a company). Such division of the characteristics of the employer brand may be appropriate, but the list of economic, functional, and psychological characteristics of the brand requires clarification.

Paper [5] states that the employer brand is a set of qualities of a company, through which it is associated with the target audience. It includes unique and positive qualities of tangible and intangible advantages of working in a company. However, it is necessary to study what qualities the employer brand should be characterized by for young people in Generation Z.

An important scientific characteristic is presented in paper [6], where the employer brand is considered as an emotional and stable image of a company in the labor market. A similar scientific confirmation of the characteristics of the employer brand is given in paper [7]. It is defined as a set of economic, professional, psychological benefits that candidates receive while working in a company. This is a set of basic values that distinguish the company in the labor market. According to [8], the employer brand is also considered as a company's reputation and image. In this case, the goal of a company is to find and attract qualified candidates for vacancies. However, the image of a company and its reputation in the labor market are created during communication between a company and existing and potential employees. Accordingly, the employer brand should include unique characteristics that make it com-

petitive and attractive in the labor market. There is a need to search for these unique characteristics.

An additional feature of the employer brand is found in research [9]. In it, the brand is characterized by two levels of the employer brand. Firstly, it is the result of the functioning of the strategy or methods for developing the employer brand and the employee's brand. Secondly, it is a complex of the company's HR brand, which includes corporate culture, communication between internal management departments, and external market participants. Probably, consideration of three levels of the employer brand is more exact: the employee's brand, the company's HR brand, the company's corporate brand. It is this view that will be most useful in the formation of value propositions of the employer for Generation Z.

The employer brand is defined as the management influence of a company in order to communicate with potential and current employees in terms of creating the most attractive place of work. The brand includes the construction of a corporate brand as the company image and a comfortable workplace for the development as a professional.

A similar proof was found in research [10], where the employer brand is defined as internal measures with effective feedback with employees, tangible and intangible motivation, an effective system for assessing personnel, the possibility of developing and training employees. It is important that this work considers one of the highest priority value propositions for Generation Z. This is the possibility of training and development of employees. However, this list is incomplete and needs to be clarified and supplemented.

Paper [11] proves that HR-brand management is a trend that affects not only the company from the inside but also determines the position of an enterprise in the labor market. A good reputation of the employer brand affects the effectiveness of HR processes, namely, it creates an opportunity to attract new talents, retains the company's staff, and allows enhancing employee motivation by 0.5 percentage points and increases profits by 0.8 percentage points. However, to determine the relationship between the reputation of the employer brand and the company's effectiveness, it is necessary to predetermine the level of development (maturity) of the employer brand. To do this, it is necessary to analyze the characteristics of its formation and, first of all, value propositions.

According to the study reported in paper [12], the corporate brand is considered an integral part of the employer brand. At the same time, the most important factors of its formation are the labor market, communication between a company and applicants, value propositions. It is most accurate to consider the employer brand as part of the company's corporate brand, and not vice versa. The list of factors for the formation of the employer brand considered in this paper is incomplete and needs to be supplemented.

A high level of the employer brand simplifies the measurement of brand capital and associativeness for job seekers [13]. The lower the level of the employer brand, the more complex and complicated the business processes of the HR department become for analysis and evaluation. Such a conclusion is appropriate, but to prove this provision, it would also be useful to formulate methodological provisions to assess the level of the employer brand.

A new direction in the field of brand management is Emotional Text Mining [14]. This means extracting brief information from a large amount of text in quick mode to understand the essence of the process. In brand management, by analogy, this can be considered as an analysis of a company as an em-

ployer in social networks. This approach is especially important for Generation Z. When searching for information about the employer, they are guided to a greater extent by social networks and a small amount of information messages. Companies should take this into account, so there is a need to minimize the number of value propositions while making them more meaningful.

According to the empirical study [15] in Germany in 2020, it was noted that the higher the level of conformity of external communication with job seekers with the actual components of the employer value proposition, the better the perception of the brand. A realistic promise to job seekers increases their loyalty and trust after being employed in a company. During the development of the brand strategy, management must maintain a high level of brand recognition and uniqueness and consistency of its formal components [16]. However, the actual components of the employer value propositions and types of external communications with job seekers need clarification.

Paper [16] considers new requirements for personnel, which are put forward by the labor market today under conditions of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. After all, the changes that occur in the context of digitalization of the economy in supply and demand in the labor market change the requirements of employers for vacancies and requirements of young people for a potential place of work. But specific skills and knowledge related to the digitalization of economic processes are not fully defined, both in terms of employer requirements and in terms of the requirements of potential job seekers.

The study [17] showed the importance of ensuring the compliance of the structure of training young people with the current and prospective needs of the labor market, and the requirements of employers. This paper also deals with the trends in the development of competencies, which are a prerequisite for determining the value propositions of employers in the labor market. That is why there is a need to critically comprehend modern trends in the development of the labor market and form a list of value propositions of an employer that meet them.

According to study [18], the dynamics of changes in supply and demand in the labor market are determined not only by the current trends of the fourth industrial revolution but also by the COVID pandemic. Thus, in the labor market today there is a transformation of the behavior of business entities at the production, consumption and management level. Thus, quarantine restrictions today require consideration and reflection in the workplace requirements of a would-be job applicant and the employer's capabilities to meet these requirements.

The employer brand as a technique for influencing the maintenance of existing employees in an IT company shows positive results [19]. In the presence of a high-quality brand, there appear brand supporters who spread information on their own. The cyclical nature of branding is manifested in the fact that, on the one hand, it acts as a source for the company's reputation in the labor market, and on the other hand, the business rating and reputation of a company should be included in the list of value propositions of the employer brand.

In the above-mentioned scientific sources [1–20], separate value propositions of employers were considered to a certain extent. However, the characteristics that affect the formation of the employer brand for Generation Z were not fully explored. There remains an unresolved problem of identifying and systematizing the most complete list of employer value propositions for Generation Z, which takes into account current labor market trends, digitalization of the economy, pandemic challenges, employers' requirements for the staff, and requirement of potential job seekers for the desired workplace.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of this study is to identify factors and components of the employer brand for Generation Z. Generation Z makes up most of the candidates for initial positions in a company. This will help employers to form an employer brand for young people, increase the number of candidates for one position, provide themselves with employees of the necessary intellectual and emotional level.

To achieve the goal, the following tasks were set:

- to analyze the rating of employer attractiveness in the labor market for Generation Z according to the results of an expert survey;
- to determine the list of value propositions to form the employer brand for Generation Z, to conduct an integrated assessment of their level of significance according to the results of an expert survey;
- to analyze the job format attractiveness for Generation Z according to the results of an expert survey.

4. The study materials and methods

The object of this research is the employer brand. The subject of the study is the theoretical and practical provisions of the formation of the employer brand.

The main hypothesis of the study is that in order to form, analyze and determine the level of the employer brand for Generation Z, it is necessary to form a list of brand value propositions and that determining the integral estimate of their significance should solve the problem of employers' formation of information messages, communication measures and value propositions for Generation Z.

Hypothetical assumption 1 is that when Generation Z chooses an internship place and decides whether to stay in a company after the internship, value propositions that are related to training and development and directly affect career formation will be the top priority.

Hypothetical assumption 2 is that for Generation Z, even after the end of the quarantine, the most attractive will be the mixed format of work, in which part of the work takes place in the office, and another part at home.

The monographic method and the method of theoretical generalization were used to determine scientific approaches to understanding the essence of the employer brand. The systemic approach was used to systematize the value propositions of an enterprise in the labor market. The method of expert evaluation was used to determine the priorities of value propositions of employment, internship, and choice of form of work during the quarantine. Graphic methods were used to illustrate theoretical and practical materials. Statistical analysis was used to analyze the results of the expert survey.

According to the results of the literature review [2, 8, 9, 11, 12, 21–24] and job sites, we generated a list of value propositions, main features, and characteristics of enterprises based on which they form the employer brand and create attractiveness in the market for a job candidate. The survey of the student audience was conducted in May 2021 in cooperation with Ukrainian universities and student organizations. The survey included 1,341 respondents who prioritized a company in each industry for internship and work. The audience of respondents included: 776 students without work experience and 565 students or graduates with experience from 1 to 5 years.

To determine the TOP companies that offer internships and vacancies for students and would take part in the study, the career sites, preliminary brand ratings of employers of TOP companies in each area, and their market share were analyzed. The TOP-9 retail companies, TOP-12 FMCG companies, and TOP-13 IT companies were selected for the study. The choice of directions of companies' activity was determined by the fact that today's students chose high-tech companies as a workplace.

The criteria of selecting a company for internships were also formed, which made it possible to compare the choice of companies by students and graduates with and without experience, to determine a convenient work schedule for students after the COVID-19 pandemic.

The expert survey was conducted online using Google Form. To analyze the results of the expert survey, Microsoft Excel software (USA) was used.

During analysis, the Pareto diagram was used, which helped to identify and visually separate 20 % of value propositions that affect 80 % of the results of employer brand formation. Using the graphic evaluation, we determined the criteria that will allow HR managers to manage the company's value propositions during the formation of the employer brand and develop a set of measures for their implementation in the activities of companies.

Mathematical processing of survey results was carried out based on the probabilism approach. In accordance with this, mathematical expectation, standard deviation, and factor of variation of the resulting survey scores were determined.

Indicators of mathematical expectation, standard deviation, and variation factor were used to summarize the survey results and determine the generalized level of significance and priority of value propositions to choose the place of internship and work by Generation Z representatives.

5. Results of the study of employer brand formation

5.1. Analysis of the rating of employer attractiveness in the labor market for Generation Z

The employer brand should be considered as a totality of internal and external factors. Firstly, it is the sum of qualities, characteristics and emotions that arise in employees and potential candidates. Secondly, it is the sum of tangible and intangible factors that form a positive image for the target audience. Thirdly, the structure of the employer brand is formed for an internal audience (employees) and external (candidates).

The employer brand for students has a unique set of characteristics. This is caused by the specifics of Generation Z. Generalization of research results made it possible to determine the main components of the employer brand for Generation Z. To determine their importance and ranking, a survey of students was conducted. The survey audience is students of Ukraine without work experience or with experience up to 1 year studying in the 3rd year of bachelor studies (23.7 %) (Fig. 1). In addition, the survey audience was studied according to the areas of study: business, law, economics, management, and sociology (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. The share of respondents according to the year of study at university

Fig. 2. The share of respondents in accordance with the major

Among retail companies, Rozetka is the priority for internships of students, 65 % of respondents chose this company (Fig. 3). This is explained more by the level of popularity of the company's trading brand than the employer brand. Rozetka is an e-commerce company that sells various goods from food staff to electronic devices. Fozzy Group, which has offline grocery stores throughout Ukraine, ranks second in the rating. The least attractive company for internships is ATB, which does not want to attract students to work. According to analysis, ATB is a more attractive workplace for candidates over the age of 40.

Among the FMCG companies, Nestle company (63.1 %) is the most attractive for students without work experience (Fig. 4). Coca-Cola HBC Ukraine ranks second. The least attractive company is Ab InBev Efes. However, companies "Corona", "Bud", "Staropramen" are popular and recognizable brands for students.

Most of the companies mentioned in the study are international. Generation Z includes young people born in 1995–2012. This allows using the research results internationally in the scientific field to form the employer brand among young people. In addition, the company Deloitte conducted a survey of 1,531 representatives of Generation Z in 2020 in the United States [15]. It was found that the peculiarities of the character, outlook, and the way of thinking of Generation Z should be taken into account by the company. First of all, 77 % of respondents are active public figures. Young people appreciate volunteer and social projects in the company and pay special attention to it. Secondly, a new trend in the labor market is the choice of work in a startup or a young company, rather than in international companies. A particularly interesting area of work is the technical field (51 %). This entails additional efforts for companies from other fields of recruitment.

Fig. 3. Top retail companies for Generation Z with or without work experience, % of respondents

Fig. 4. TOP companies in FMCG for Generation Z with and without work experience, % of respondents

All this allows arguing that the influence of a generation on the formation of the employer brand and brand components can be applied internationally. This is due to similar problems and behavior of modern youth.

5. 2. Determining, analysis, and integrated evaluation of the significance of value propositions for choosing an internship place for Generation Z

Processing the survey results showed that the most important factors for choosing an internship place for students are the opportunity of training at a company (56.96 %), the salary level (44.79 %), official employment (40.85 %). These factors must be included in the vacancy description and promo text for recruitment for internship programs. The company’s business rating and reputation

(29.91 %), internship schedule (39.05 %), additional benefits (21.11 %), and the status of an international company (16.86 %) are important but not the major factors. The least important factors are the possibility of relocation to another city /country (16.75 %) and the level of the company’s scale (12.10 %).

Fig. 5 shows the results of an expert survey on determining the priority of value propositions of the employer brand for students with or without work experience when choosing a company for internship.

To summarize the results of assessing the level of significance of factors for choosing a company for an internship, we used the probabilistic approach, which is based on determining mathematical expectation, root mean square deviation, and coefficient of variation of the survey rating results.

Fig. 5. Rating the level of importance of value propositions for students with or without work experience when choosing a company for internship, number of respondents

The significance of factors was assessed by the following categories: unimportant (grade 1); least important (grade 2); important (grade 3); very important (grade 4). Thus, a scale of estimates of the significance level from 1 to 4 was used.

At stage 1, the probability of obtaining an appropriate estimate for each factor is determined from the formula:

$$X_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^4 a_{ij}}, \tag{1}$$

where X_{ij} is the probability of obtaining score j for the i -th factor; a_{ij} is the number of students who gave score j to factor i ; i is the factor index ($i=1, \dots, n$); n is the number of factors; j is the value of the factor score ($j=1, \dots, 4$).

As a result, we get a matrix of probabilities of scores of answers to questionnaire questions:

$$\begin{matrix} X_{11} & X_{12} & X_{13} & X_{14} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ X_1 & X_2 & X_3 & X_4 \end{matrix} \tag{2}$$

Each line of this matrix is a grouped statistical series of probabilities of obtaining the j -th score for each i -th studied factor of the system of assessment of choosing a company for internship.

Thus, for a generalized assessment of the factor, it is possible to choose indicators of mathematical expectation, root mean square deviation, and variation factor.

The mathematical expectation of the score for each i -th factor can be calculated from the formula:

$$M(X_i) = \sum_{j=1}^4 j \cdot X_{ij}. \tag{3}$$

The mathematical expectation of the factor scores shows the average score of the factor according to a four-point scale.

Root mean square deviation for each i -th factor is calculated from the formula:

$$\sigma(X_i) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^4 (j - M(X_i))^2 \cdot X_{ij}}. \tag{4}$$

Root mean square deviation shows the magnitude of fluctuations in the score of each factor around its mathematical expectation.

Variation factor is calculated from the formula:

$$CV(X_i) = \frac{\sigma(X_i)}{M(X_i)} \cdot 100 \%. \tag{5}$$

Variation factor shows how many fluctuations in percentage fall per unit of the expected score of the factors. With the help of this indicator, it is possible to determine how large the differences in the assessment of this factor by students are. The results of statistical analysis of the survey results are shown in Table 1.

The factor of variation of the survey results showed the magnitude of differences in the scores of respondents for each factor under study. The least similar among respondents is the opinion about the possibility of relocation to other countries. This factor has the greatest divergence in

the respondents' opinions. The most similar is the assessment of the possibility of training in a company (20.13 %).

According to the generalized assessment of the level of significance of the factor, it is possible to construct a Pareto diagram (Fig. 6). With the help of such analysis, it is possible to identify the most significant factors for determining the place of internship and work, which account for 80 % of students' choices to substantiate the place of internship and work. That is, these factors determine 80 % of the company's attractiveness for students when choosing an internship place.

Table 1

Integrated score of the significance of value propositions at choosing an internship place by representatives of Generation Z

Value propositions	Probability of obtained scores				$M(X_j)$	$\sigma(X_j)$	$CV(X_j)$
Level of company's scale (for example, the number of countries, where a company is represented)	0.17	0.36	0.35	0.12	2.43	0.91	37.41
Possibility of relocation to another city/country	0.19	0.32	0.31	0.17	2.45	0.99	40.18
Additional benefits (insurance, working place, etc.)	0.09	0.30	0.40	0.21	2.73	0.89	32.57
Active social position of CEO	0.12	0.28	0.39	0.21	2.70	0.93	34.63
Working in an international company	0.09	0.29	0.40	0.22	2.74	0.90	32.91
Office location	0.07	0.30	0.39	0.24	2.80	0.88	31.36
Positive impact of good/services on the environment	0.11	0.28	0.35	0.25	2.74	0.96	35.07
Balance of "good actions" and profit	0.08	0.25	0.38	0.28	2.87	0.92	32.15
Business rating and reputation of a company	0.04	0.20	0.46	0.29	3.01	0.81	26.94
Internship schedule	0.04	0.15	0.41	0.39	3.15	0.83	26.50
Official employment	0.08	0.21	0.30	0.41	3.03	0.98	32.17
Salary level	0.02	0.13	0.40	0.45	3.27	0.77	23.61
Training in company	0.01	0.09	0.33	0.57	3.46	0.70	20.13

Analyzing the Pareto diagram (Fig. 6), we can say that working in an international company creates additional benefits for students in the form of the possibility of relocation to another country/city and the scale level. These factors do not require additional attention of management but can be included.

It is possible to rank factors by the degree of importance using the Sturges method of analytical grouping, according to which the grouping interval is determined from the formula:

$$I_{M(X)} = \frac{M(X)_{\max} - M(X)_{\min}}{1 + 3,322 \cdot \lg n}, \tag{6}$$

$M(X)_{\max}$ and $M(X)_{\min}$ are, respectively, maximum and minimum values of mathematical expectation of significance of factors; n is the number of unit of totality.

Fig. 6. Pareto diagram for analysis of value propositions for choosing an internship place by representatives of Generation Z (by their level of significance)

Table 2 shows the identification of the integrated score of the significance of the factors by which students choose the internship place and determines the factors that were included in these categories of assessment.

Categorizing the level of importance of the factors in students' choice of an internship place allows the company to focus its efforts and resources on solving the most sig-

nificant aspects of management during the employer brand formation.

Using (1) to (5), the importance of factors for students after the internship to continue working in the company was assessed. Fig. 7 shows the ranking of actors that influenced the decision to stay in the company after the internship for Generation Z according to an expert survey.

Table 2

Grouping the values of integrated score of the significance of the factors when choosing the internship place by Generation Z representatives

Integrated score of factors' significances	Category of factors' significance	Qualitative characteristic	Factors included in this range
[2,43; 2,63]	Low	The level of impact of factors is low, they meet the requirements of only a small number of students and are the least productive to create the attractiveness of the employer brand	Possibility of relocation to another city/country, business rating of a company
[2,63; 2,83]	Below average	Factors are not able to actively adapt to most of the requests of students regarding the choice of internship place, their impact on the company attractiveness is not decisive	Office location, work in an international company, active social position of CEO, additional benefits
[2,83; 3,03]	Average	The level of impact of the factors is average, they meet the conditions of the requests of some students, some of them are on the boundary of making decisions on the choice of an internship place	Balance between good actions and profit
[3,03; 3,23]	Above average	The level of impact of factors is high, they are attractive enough for most students when choosing an internship place	Official employment, internship schedule
[3,23; 3,47]	High	Factors have the most productive impact on students' choice of internship place and create attractiveness of the employer brand in the market	Salary level, training in company

Fig. 7. The results of assessment of the factors influencing the decision to stay for working in a company after internship for representatives of generation Z, the number of respondents

The most important factors influencing the decision to stay after an internship at the company are the ability to combine work and study at university (average score 3.59 out of 4), team (3.54), and access to training at the company (3.54) (Fig. 7). Score 4 is the highest. The factors that need to be included in the internship program are a flexible schedule and the possibility to work remotely, the presence of a mentor for the internship period, the opportunity to study at the company and develop as a professional (Fig. 7).

The tasks set for the internship period, the importance of a project for a company, and the adaptation program in a company are important but not priorities. The least important factors are work in different departments and international experience.

5. 3. Analysis of the attractiveness of the work format for generation Z

After the pandemic, a convenient work schedule for students is three working days in the office and two working days remotely (31.3 %) (Fig. 8). The remote format of work combined with meetings with the team in the office ranks second (22.7 %). The hybrid format is ideal. Employees can choose their own work schedule. It should be added that only the remote format of work is unacceptable for students (13.4 %).

63.4 % of Generation Z plan to work in the specialty (63.4 %). Accordingly, this is an ideal option for a company, since the process of finding candidates for internships will be easier for the HR team. Only 5.7 % of respondents do not plan to work in the specialty.

Fig. 8. The share of surveyed representatives of Generation Z regarding convenient work format

6. Discussion of the results of the research into employer brand formation for Generation Z

The study of the priority place of work for representatives of Generation Z was conducted to identify the best practices for the formation of value propositions by modern companies that willingly hire young people. Indirectly, this determines the companies with effective employer brands. It was found that the most desirable place of work for Generation Z in the retail sector is Rozetka (Fig. 3), which is caused by the popularity of the trade brand, the level of informatization of business processes in the company, flexible work schedule. In the FMCG area, company Nestle, which is an innovative company that values creativity of thinking and can give experience under international business rules, turned out to be the best company for a potential job (Fig. 4). The least attractive workplaces are ATB and Ab InBev Efes (Fig. 3, 4, respectively). Unlike [5], which indicates only attractive areas for generation Z, the results of the study revealed exemplary companies with an established employer brand. This allows additional analysis of the most attractive employers' best practices regarding the formed value propositions.

The review of literary sources [1, 2, 4–7, 11–13, 16–21] allowed constructing a list of value propositions of employers for Generation Z. Mandatory components are training in a company, salary level, official employment, internship schedule, additional benefits, business rating and reputation of a company. Secondary components include the balance between “good actions” and profit, the positive impact of goods/services on the environment, the location of the company, work in an international company, an active social position, the possible relocation, the scale level.

A high level of the employer brand in HR management is defined as the formation of a value proposition for employees and job seekers with unique qualities and characteristics for a company in the labor market. A mandatory characteristic of the employer brand is the attraction of talents and the creation of a competitive enterprise [9, 15]. It is considered from two positions: marketing and management, that is, it has a focus on two target audiences [7, 13, 16]. Also, the employer brand has an emotional connotation and creates a certain image for job seekers, which is associated only with a certain company [19, 20]. It was found that the effective employer brand has a positive effect on the company's performance [14, 21].

The results of the quantitative analysis of the survey on the attractiveness of value propositions made it possible to identify their specific features for Generation Z. Analysis of the survey revealed the most and least attractive factors when choosing an internship place. The highest priority factors are the salary level (348 respondents) and training in a company (442 respondents) (Fig. 5 and Table 2). The lowest factors include the level of the company's scale and the possibility of relocation to another city or country (Fig. 5 and Table 2).

For the integrated evaluation of value propositions, we used the Pareto diagram, which is common in the field of personnel management and allows identifying 20 % of the most significant factors that give the employer brand an 80 % success rate (Fig. 6). Unlike [15], where company Deloitte, USA identified only general changes in the values and behavior of Generation Z, analysis conducted in this study enables an employer to form a better value proposition for Generation Z. Thanks to this analysis, the

description of internship positions will be more attractive for candidates.

Due to the global pandemic, there have been changes in HR processes in companies. First of all, it is the work format of the company's employees. Most of them were transferred to a remote work schedule in order to avoid the spread of morbidity. The hybrid schedule turned out to be most convenient for Generation Z, even in the absence of quarantine restrictions (Fig. 8). This is a work format of employees, in which they work three days in the office and two – remotely (Fig. 8). Unlike [15], where there is no information about the work format as a component of the value proposition of the employer brand, this allows creating new value propositions during the formation of the employer brand for Generation Z, which can be effectively used by companies not only in the context of a global pandemic but also when designing changes in HR processes in companies.

The complex comprehensively considers and identifies the main value propositions that are of the most and least priority for Generation Z. When choosing value propositions, modern labor market trends, digitalization of the economy, the COVID-19 pandemic were taken into account.

The drawback of the study is the lack of open questions. Elimination of this drawback would lead to an increase in the difficulty of processing survey results, which is not justified.

Further research will be aimed at the construction of a methodological toolkit for evaluating the employer brand and organization of management activities for its formation by enterprises.

7. Conclusions

1. According to the results of the survey, the main modern trends of the employer brand in the labor market were analyzed, indicating their rating of attractiveness for Generation Z. Among the 9 leading retail companies, “Rozetka”, “Fozzy Group” and “Comfy” were the most attractive for Generation Z, according to the results of the survey. Among 13 leading companies in the FMCG sphere, “Nestle” and “Coca-Cola HBC Ukraine” were the most attractive for Generation Z. This allowed revealing the best companies that use the employer brand when searching for staff, and whose experience can be used as best management practices.

2. Based on the results of the study, it was found that in order to form the employer brand, it is necessary to take into account and balance the qualities and characteristics of potential candidates for employment. In accordance with this, the employer brand should be considered from the point of view of the requirements of an enterprise for them and the value proposition of companies in the labor market. Generation Z as potential employees is attractive to today's employers, who expect their employees to have creativity, energy, and opportunities to learn and develop with the company. However, to do this, companies need to form specific value propositions that would satisfy this target audience. With the help of established value propositions, companies position themselves in the labor market and create their own image for potential employees. A list of the main value propositions that are important for Generation Z when choosing a place of work and internship was formed. As a result of the survey, the priority of value propositions for Generation Z choosing a place of work and internship was determined. The

following value propositions received the greatest importance for choosing a place of work: salary level and training in the company. The possibility of relocating to another city/country and the company's business rating were of the least importance. The following value propositions turned out to be most important for choosing an internship: salary level and training in a company. The possibility of relocating to another city/country and the company's business rating were the least important. Internships are an important part of staff selection; it makes it possible to accurately identify the most suitable employees for a company. On the one hand, potential employees should understand and evaluate the would-be employment. On the other hand, employers do not want to spend extra money and time searching for the necessary personnel. The study of the priority of the factors, considering which representatives of Generation Z decide to stay in the company after an internship showed tangible and intangible incentives that guide them. The most important are: the salary level and training in the company. The least important are the possibility of relocating to another city country and the company's business rating. This indicates a certain balance of tangible (salary) and intangible (training opportunities) value propositions when choosing a company both for internships and for work after an internship. Openness,

flexibility, and dynamism of the behavioral characteristics of Generation Z representatives make the value proposition to relocate to another city/country unimportant for them. And the absence of authority leads to the low priority of business rating and the reputation of a company.

3. Quarantine restrictions significantly affected the organization of work with the staff and the search for job candidates. The study showed which factors are most attractive to Generation Z under conditions of remote work. Thus, the most attractive is the schedule in which employees work three days in the office and 2 days remotely. The least attractive is the schedule when employees work remotely 5 days a week. This indicates the desire of representatives of Generation Z to plan their time independently, to have spare time for development and training in attractive areas of interest.

The content and the level of significance of value propositions for Generation Z will allow companies to better understand their target audience when forming their own employer brand and focus on the necessary aspects of managing their present and would-be staff. The peculiarities of the character, behavior, way of thinking, and attitude to life and work of Generation Z should be taken into account to form the employer brand.

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